

RADICALZ

Version 2

Description

3rd version of the RadicalZ DMP (M27)

Funder

European Commission||
EC

Grant

RAPID DISCOVERY AND
DEVELOPMENT OF
ENZYMES FOR NOVEL
AND GREENER
CONSUMER PRODUCTS/
No 101000560

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Organizations

INSA de Toulouse, Ecole Polytechnique Federal de Lausanne, Chr. Hansen (Denmark), BIO-PRODIGT BV, Universidad Autónoma de Madrid, SUSTAINABLE MOMENTUM SL, SCIENSEED SL, BIOTECHNOLOGY RESEARCH AND INFORMATION NETWORK AG, AnalytiCon Discovery GmbH, University of Exeter, University of Greifswald, SVEUCILISTE U ZAGREBU FAKULTET KEMIJSKOG INZENJERSTVA I TEHNOLOGIJE

Datasets

Title: Protein structures

Template: Horizon 2020

Protein structures based on x-ray diffraction and/or computational modelling.

Dataset Description

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

- To obtain information
- To make informed decisions
- To develop a product

1.1.2 What types of data will the project generate/collect?

- text mining
- sample or specimen data
- experimental (e.g.
- gene sequencing data)
- derived or compiled (e.g.
- text mining
- 3D models)

1.1.3 What formats of data will the project generate/collect?

- Text files
- Discipline specific formats

PDB format

1.1.4 What is the origin of the data?

- Primary data
- Secondary data

1.1.5 What is the expected size of the data?

GB (gigabyte)

1.1.6 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Education
- Economy

2.1 Reused Data

2.1.1 Will you re-use any existing data and how?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 Will you use metadata to describe the data?

Yes

PDBx/mmCIF (Protein Data Bank Exchange Dictionary and the Macromolecular Crystallographic Information Framework)

3.1.1.3 Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

3.1.1.5 Will you make the metadata available free-of-charge?

Yes

3.1.1.6 Will your metadata be harvestable?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

Yes

3.1.1.10 Will you provide persistent identifiers for your data?

Yes

3.1.1.11 Persistent identifiers

Other

crystal structures will be assigned a PDB code, models a DOI

3.1.1.12 Will you provide searchable metadata for your data?

Yes

3.1.1.15 Will you use standardised formats for your data?

Yes

3.1.1.18 Are the file formats you will use open?

Yes

3.1.1.20 Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

Yes

3.1.1.22 Will you provide metadata describing the quality of the data?

Yes

3.1.2 Making data openly accessible

3.1.2.1 Are there ethical or legal issues that can impact sharing the data?

No

3.1.2.2 Will your data be openly accessible?

some

Comment:

Selected datasets cleared for dissemination by the IP work package.

3.1.2.4 How will the data be made available?

Domain-specific database

RCSB Protein Data Bank

3.1.2.7 Are there any methods or tools required to access the data?

Yes

3.1.3 Making data interoperable

3.1.3.1 Will you use a controlled vocabulary for your data?

Yes

3.1.4 Increase data reuse

3.1.4.1 When do you plan to make your data available for reuse?

end of project

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 How will the cost of making your data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable be covered?

- Use of institution infrastructure
- Other

4.1.2 Will you identify a data manager to manage your data, if not who will be responsible for the management of your data?

Yes

4.1.3 Identify the people or roles that will be responsible for the management of the project data

Aurelio Hidalgo (orcid:0000-0001-5740-5584)

Responsible of procuring data curation and upload services

4.1.4 How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?

Institutional archive

Comment:

Zenodo will be used as a repository

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What do you plan to do with research data of limited use?

Kept on secure, managed storage for limited time

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

No

6.1.2 What are the methods used for processing sensitive/personal data?

Anonymising data where necessary

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Title: Communication materials

Template: Horizon 2020

Communication materials of RADICALZ project until Month 24

Dataset Description

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

- To share information
- To make informed decisions
- To combine with other data

1.1.2 What types of data will the project generate/collect?

Other

videos, infographics, images, text

1.1.3 What formats of data will the project generate/collect?

- Text files
- Multimedia

1.1.4 What is the origin of the data?

- Primary data
- Secondary data

1.1.5 What is the expected size of the data?

GB (gigabyte)

1.1.6 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities

- Decision makers
- Education
- The public
- Industry

2.1 Reused Data

2.1.1 Will you re-use any existing data and how?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 Will you use metadata to describe the data?

No

3.1.1.3 Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.7 Will you use naming conventions for your data?

No

3.1.1.9 Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

Yes

3.1.1.10 Will you provide persistent identifiers for your data?

Yes

3.1.1.11 Persistent identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.12 Will you provide searchable metadata for your data?

No

3.1.1.15 Will you use standardised formats for your data?

Yes

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

3.1.1.16 Provide information about used standardised formats

.odt., .rtf, .png, .txt, .mpg

3.1.1.18 Are the file formats you will use open?

Yes

Comment:

.odt., .rtf, .png, .txt, .mpg

3.1.1.20 Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

Yes

3.1.1.22 Will you provide metadata describing the quality of the data?

No

3.1.2 Making data openly accessible

3.1.2.1 Are there ethical or legal issues that can impact sharing the data?

No

3.1.2.2 Will your data be openly accessible?

all

3.1.2.4 How will the data be made available?

- Project website
- Repository of Archive

<https://zenodo.org>; <https://radicalz.eu>

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

3.1.2.5 Please provide URL/Name of used data repositories

<https://radicalz.eu>; <https://zenodo.org>

3.1.2.6 Is the storage sufficiently secure for the data and does the storage provide backup and recovery procedures?

secure with backup and recovery

3.1.2.7 Are there any methods or tools required to access the data?

No

3.1.2.10 Will you also make auxiliary data that may be of interest to researchers available?

no auxiliary data

3.1.3 Making data interoperable

3.1.3.1 Will you use a controlled vocabulary for your data?

Yes

3.1.4 Increase data reuse

3.1.4.1 When do you plan to make your data available for reuse?

immediately

3.1.4.5 Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of your data?

No

3.1.4.8 Will you provide any support for data reuse?

No

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 How will the cost of making your data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.2 Will you identify a data manager to manage your data, if not who will be responsible for the management of your data?

Yes

4.1.3 Identify the people or roles that will be responsible for the management of the project data

Aurelio Hidalgo (orcid:0000-0001-5740-5584)

Responsible of procuring curation and deposit services

4.1.4 How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?

Institutional archive

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What do you plan to do with research data of limited use?

Kept on secure, managed storage for limited time

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

No

6.1.2 What are the methods used for processing sensitive/personal data?

Anonymising data where necessary

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Title: [Metagenomic DNA sequences](#)

Template: [Horizon 2020](#)

Environmental DNA samples from extreme environments will be taken and sequenced to find enzymes relevant to the activities of the project.

Dataset Description

1.1 Data Summary

[1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?](#)

- To obtain information
- To develop a product

Comment:

Metagenomic DNA sequences contain information about the relative abundance of different microorganisms in a given environment and can be mined using adequate bioinformatics tools to find genes encoding enzymes of interest for the objectives of RadicalZ

[1.1.2 What types of data will the project generate/collect?](#)

- sample or specimen data
- experimental (e.g.
- gene sequencing data)

Coordinates of place of sampling, physicochemical characteristics (aggregation state, temperature, pH), results from NGS sequencing

[1.1.3 What formats of data will the project generate/collect?](#)

- Text files
- Numerical

Raw data from individual reads, processed files for assembled contigs and processed data (ORF assignation, functional annotation)

[1.1.4 What is the origin of the data?](#)

Primary data

1.1.5 What is the expected size of the data?

TB (terabyte)

1.1.6 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Economy

Data will be useful to the research community for taxonomic purposes and to the research community and industrial stakeholders for further mining with commercial interest.

2.1 Reused Data

2.1.1 Will you re-use any existing data and how?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 Will you use metadata to describe the data?

Yes

MIBBI (Minimum Information for Biological and Biomedical Investigations)

3.1.1.3 Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

3.1.1.5 Will you make the metadata available free-of-charge?

Yes

3.1.1.6 Will your metadata be harvestable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 Will you use naming conventions for your data?

No

3.1.1.9 Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

Yes

3.1.1.10 Will you provide persistent identifiers for your data?

Yes

3.1.1.11 Persistent identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.12 Will you provide searchable metadata for your data?

Yes

3.1.1.15 Will you use standardised formats for your data?

Yes

3.1.1.18 Are the file formats you will use open?

Yes

3.1.1.20 Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

Yes

Zenodo

3.1.1.21 Please describe if data require proprietary tools to access the data?

No

3.1.2 Making data openly accessible

3.1.2.1 Are there ethical or legal issues that can impact sharing the data?

No

3.1.2.2 Will your data be openly accessible?

some

Comment:

Selected datasets cleared for dissemination by the IP work package.

3.1.2.4 How will the data be made available?

Domain-specific database

MGnify

3.1.2.7 Are there any methods or tools required to access the data?

No

3.1.3 Making data interoperable

3.1.3.1 Will you use a controlled vocabulary for your data?

Yes

3.1.4 Increase data reuse

3.1.4.1 When do you plan to make your data available for reuse?

end of project

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 How will the cost of making your data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable be covered?

- Use of institution infrastructure
- Other

4.1.2 Will you identify a data manager to manage your data, if not who will be responsible for the management of your data?

Yes

4.1.3 Identify the people or roles that will be responsible for the management of the project data

Aurelio Hidalgo (orcid:0000-0001-5740-5584)

Responsible of procuring curation and deposit services

4.1.4 How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?

Other

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What do you plan to do with research data of limited use?

Kept on secure, managed storage for limited time

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

No

6.1.2 What are the methods used for processing sensitive/personal data?

Anonymising data where necessary

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Title: Dissemination data

Template: Horizon 2020

Dissemination data of RADICALZ project until Month 24

Dataset Description

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

- To share information
- To keep on record
- To make informed decisions
- To develop a product
- To improve a product
- To combine with other data

1.1.2 What types of data will the project generate/collect?

Other

Articles, posters, patents

1.1.3 What formats of data will the project generate/collect?

Text files

1.1.4 What is the origin of the data?

- Primary data
- Secondary data

1.1.5 What is the expected size of the data?

GB (gigabyte)

1.1.6 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- Education
- The public
- Industry

2.1 Reused Data

2.1.1 Will you re-use any existing data and how?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 Will you use metadata to describe the data?

No

3.1.1.3 Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.7 Will you use naming conventions for your data?

No

3.1.1.9 Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

Yes

3.1.1.10 Will you provide persistent identifiers for your data?

Yes

3.1.1.11 Persistent identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.12 Will you provide searchable metadata for your data?

No

3.1.1.15 Will you use standardised formats for your data?

Yes

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

3.1.1.16 Provide information about used standardised formats

.odt, .pdf, .txt, .png, .rtf

3.1.1.18 Are the file formats you will use open?

Yes

3.1.1.20 Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

Yes

Comment:

Open Office

3.1.1.22 Will you provide metadata describing the quality of the data?

No

3.1.2 Making data openly accessible

3.1.2.1 Are there ethical or legal issues that can impact sharing the data?

No

3.1.2.2 Will your data be openly accessible?

all

3.1.2.4 How will the data be made available?

- Project website
- Repository of Archive

<https://zenodo.org>; <https://radicalz.eu>

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

3.1.2.5 Please provide URL/Name of used data repositories

<https://zenodo.org>; <https://radicalz.eu>

<https://zenodo.org>

3.1.2.6 Is the storage sufficiently secure for the data and does the storage provide backup and recovery procedures?

secure with backup and recovery

3.1.2.7 Are there any methods or tools required to access the data?

No

3.1.2.10 Will you also make auxiliary data that may be of interest to researchers available?

no auxiliary data

3.1.3 Making data interoperable

3.1.3.1 Will you use a controlled vocabulary for your data?

Yes

3.1.4 Increase data reuse

3.1.4.1 When do you plan to make your data available for reuse?

immediately

3.1.4.5 Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of your data?

No

3.1.4.8 Will you provide any support for data reuse?

No

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 How will the cost of making your data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.2 Will you identify a data manager to manage your data, if not who will be responsible for the management of your data?

Yes

4.1.3 Identify the people or roles that will be responsible for the management of the project data

Aurelio Hidalgo (orcid:0000-0001-5740-5584)

Responsible of procuring data curation and upload services

4.1.4 How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?

Institutional archive

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What do you plan to do with research data of limited use?

Kept on secure, managed storage for limited time

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

No

6.1.2 What are the methods used for processing sensitive/personal data?

Anonymising data where necessary

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Title: [Enzyme properties](#)

Template: [Horizon 2020](#)

Characteristics of enzymes and/or enzyme variants, such as steady state kinetic parameters, T_{opt} , pH_{opt} , thermostability, enantioselectivity, substrate scope

Dataset Description

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

- To obtain information
- To make informed decisions
- To develop a product

1.1.2 What types of data will the project generate/collect?

- text mining
- sample or specimen data
- experimental (e.g.
- gene sequencing data)
- derived or compiled (e.g.
- text mining
- 3D models)

1.1.3 What formats of data will the project generate/collect?

- Text files
- Numerical
- Models
- Discipline specific formats
- Instrument specific formats

1.1.4 What is the origin of the data?

- Primary data
- Secondary data

1.1.5 What is the expected size of the data?

GB (gigabyte)

1.1.6 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Education
- Industry

2.1 Reused Data

2.1.1 Will you re-use any existing data and how?

Yes

ProteinGym data, as described on <https://www.proteingym.org/> to evaluate ML-assisted protein engineering methodologies.

To reproduce and validate findings

2.1.2 Where do the data reside?

Data is accessible via a GitHub repository:
<https://github.com/OATML-Markslab/ProteinGym>

2.1.3 Which data will be re-used?

Substitution datasets from the ProteinGym, located here:
https://marks.hms.harvard.edu/proteingym/ProteinGym_substitutions.zip

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 Will you use metadata to describe the data?

Yes

MIBBI (Minimum Information for Biological and Biomedical Investigations)

3.1.1.3 Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

3.1.1.5 Will you make the metadata available free-of-charge?

Yes

3.1.1.6 Will your metadata be harvestable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 Will you use naming conventions for your data?

Yes

3.1.1.8 Please provide more details and examples on used naming conversions

<https://fairsharing.org/collection/MIBBI>

3.1.1.9 Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

Yes

3.1.1.10 Will you provide persistent identifiers for your data?

Yes

3.1.1.11 Persistent identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.12 Will you provide searchable metadata for your data?

Yes

3.1.1.15 Will you use standardised formats for your data?

Yes

3.1.1.18 Are the file formats you will use open?

Yes

3.1.1.20 Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

Yes

3.1.1.22 Will you provide metadata describing the quality of the data?

Yes

3.1.2 Making data openly accessible

3.1.2.1 Are there ethical or legal issues that can impact sharing the data?

No

3.1.2.2 Will your data be openly accessible?

some

Comment:

Selected datasets cleared for dissemination by the IP work package.

3.1.2.4 How will the data be made available?

Zenodo

3.1.2.7 Are there any methods or tools required to access the data?

No

3.1.2.10 Will you also make auxiliary data that may be of interest to researchers available?

no auxiliary data

3.1.3 Making data interoperable

3.1.3.1 Will you use a controlled vocabulary for your data?

Yes

3.1.4 Increase data reuse

3.1.4.1 When do you plan to make your data available for reuse?

end of project

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.2 Will you identify a data manager to manage your data, if not who will be responsible for the management of your data?

Yes

4.1.3 Identify the people or roles that will be responsible for the management of the project data

Aurelio Hidalgo (orcid:0000-0001-5740-5584)

Responsible of procuring curation and deposit services

4.1.4 How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?

- Institutional archive

- Other

Zenodo

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What do you plan to do with research data of limited use?

Kept on secure, managed storage for limited time

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

No

6.1.2 What are the methods used for processing sensitive/personal data?

Anonymising data where necessary

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Title: Kinetic models of enzyme reactions

Template: Horizon 2020

Kinetic models of the targeted reaction systems will be developed and used for reaction optimization. Data will be provided in the form of equations in .txt or word format.

Dataset Description

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

To share information

Comment:

The kinetic models enable reactor selection, optimization of reaction conditions, calculation of LCA, techno-economic analysis of the process.

1.1.2 What types of data will the project generate/collect?

- simulation (e.g.
- climate modeling data)
- derived or compiled (e.g.
- text mining
- 3D models)

1.1.3 What formats of data will the project generate/collect?

- Text files
- Models

1.1.4 What is the origin of the data?

Secondary data

1.1.5 What is the expected size of the data?

MB (megabyte)

Comment:

Data will occupy low amount of memory. It will be provided in several rows depending on the amount of equations/reactions.

1.1.6 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Education
- Industry

2.1 Reused Data

2.1.1 Will you re-use any existing data and how?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 Will you use metadata to describe the data?

Yes

3.1.1.3 Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

3.1.1.5 Will you make the metadata available free-of-charge?

Yes

Comment:

Data will be made public in Zenodo

3.1.1.6 Will your metadata be harvestable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 Will you use naming conventions for your data?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

Yes

3.1.1.10 Will you provide persistent identifiers for your data?

Yes

3.1.1.11 Persistent identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.12 Will you provide searchable metadata for your data?

Yes

3.1.1.13 What services will you use to provide searchable metadata?

Metadata repository

3.1.1.15 Will you use standardised formats for your data?

Yes

3.1.1.18 Are the file formats you will use open?

Yes

Comment:

txt, rtf, odt

3.1.1.20 Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

Yes

3.1.1.22 Will you provide metadata describing the quality of the data?

Yes

3.1.2 Making data openly accessible

3.1.2.1 Are there ethical or legal issues that can impact sharing the data?

No

3.1.2.2 Will your data be openly accessible?

some

3.1.2.3 Please provide the URL of the data which can be made available

<https://zenodo.org>

3.1.2.4 How will the data be made available?

Other

Zenodo

3.1.2.6 Is the storage sufficiently secure for the data and does the storage provide backup and recovery procedures?

secure with backup and recovery

3.1.2.7 Are there any methods or tools required to access the data?

No

3.1.2.10 Will you also make auxiliary data that may be of interest to researchers available?

after publication

3.1.3 Making data interoperable

3.1.3.1 Will you use a controlled vocabulary for your data?

Yes

3.1.4 Increase data reuse

3.1.4.1 When do you plan to make your data available for reuse?

after article publication

3.1.4.5 Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of your data?

No

3.1.4.8 Will you provide any support for data reuse?

No

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 How will the cost of making your data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable be covered?

- Use of institution infrastructure
- Other

4.1.2 Will you identify a data manager to manage your data, if not who will be responsible for the management of your data?

Yes

Comment:

Aurelio Hidalgo

Zvezdana findrik

Martina Sudar

4.1.3 Identify the people or roles that will be responsible for the management of the project data

Martina Sudar (orcid:0000-0002-6734-1024)

4.1.4 How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?

Other

Zenodo

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What do you plan to do with research data of limited use?

Kept on secure, managed storage for limited time

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

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